

LOW-FREQUENCY CAPACITANCE-VOLTAGE CHARACTERISTICS OF METAL-DIELECTRIC- SEMICONDUCTOR STRUCTURES

¹Kuchkarova M.O., ²Kholboyeva N.B.

¹Senior Lecturer, Department of Physics, Andijan State University

²Senior teacher, Department of Physics, Namangan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14563408>

Abstract. Interest in studying physical processes occurring on the surfaces of solids has emerged due to the significant influence of surface phenomena on bulk physical processes and the performance of most solid-state devices.

Keywords: microminiaturization, metal-dielectric-semiconductor, Fermi level, Poisson equation, semiconductor capacitance, capacitance-voltage characteristics, density.

Introduction. Surface physics is inherently an interdisciplinary field of knowledge, encompassing research areas relevant to both physics and chemistry. From an applied perspective, it is a science critical to addressing challenges in materials science, micro- and nanoelectronics, energy, and space technology. One of the most significant branches of surface science is the physics of semiconductor surfaces.

The surface can be viewed as a novel thin semiconductor material or a reduced-dimensional system, which is of great interest due to increasing demands for the microminiaturization of semiconductor devices. The low-frequency method of investigation is based on the assumption that, at sufficiently low-test signal frequencies, all electronic states localized both in the transition layer between the semiconductor and dielectric, as well as in the boundary region of the semiconductor, have enough time to exchange electrons with the allowed energy bands of the semiconductor [1].

This phenomenon occurs under conditions of a slowly varying electric field intensity created by the test signal and under constant bias voltage. Charges localized in the boundary region of the semiconductor and the transition layer, through their exchange of electrons with the allowed energy bands of the semiconductor, make an additional contribution to the capacitance of the transition layer and, consequently, to the capacitance of the entire metal-dielectric-semiconductor structure.

Method. For definiteness, let us consider the boundary region of an n-type semiconductor. The expression for the volume charge density in this region, taking into account the contribution of free charge carriers, has the following form:

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}) = q(N_d - N_a + p - n) \quad (1)$$

Here: n_i is the concentration of intrinsic charge carriers in the semiconductor; k is the Boltzmann constant; T is the temperature; φ_0 is the energy gap between the Fermi level for electrons and the middle of the semiconductor's forbidden zone [2]. At sufficiently high temperatures, the concentration of free charge carriers in the semiconductor is determined by the concentration of ionized dopants, i.e.

$$n-p=N_d-N_a:$$

$$N_d - N_a = n_i \left[\exp\left(\frac{q\varphi_0}{kT}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{q\varphi_0}{kT}\right) \right] = 2n_i \operatorname{sh}\left(\frac{q\varphi_0}{kT}\right) \quad (3)$$

The distribution of the difference in concentrations of free electrons and holes as a function of the coordinate x in the near-surface region of the semiconductor ($x=0$ corresponds to the semiconductor-dielectric interface) is given as follows:

$$n(x) - p(x) = n_i 2 \operatorname{sh}\left[\frac{q\varphi(x)}{kT}\right] \quad (4)$$

By introducing dimensionless quantities:

$$\psi_0 = \frac{q\varphi_0}{kT}; \quad \psi(x) = \frac{q\varphi(x)}{kT} \quad (5)$$

And using Poisson's equation, which relates the change in potential with the coordinate to the volume charge density in the semiconductor, we obtain:

$$\frac{d^2\psi(x)}{dx^2} = \frac{1}{L^2} [\operatorname{sh}\psi(x) - \operatorname{sh}\psi_0] \quad (6)$$

Here: $L^2 = \frac{kT\epsilon T_0}{2q^2 n_i}$ - Debye characteristic length; ϵ - relative permittivity of the semiconductor; ϵ_0 - permittivity of vacuum [3]. Integration of equation (6) makes it possible to derive an expression for the electric field intensity in the near-surface region of the semiconductor as a function of the concentration of majority charge carriers, surface potential, and temperature:

$$E_s = -\frac{d\varphi}{dx} = \frac{kT}{q} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{L} F(\psi_s; \psi_0) \quad (7)$$

here: $F^2(\psi_s; \psi_0) = [\operatorname{sh}\psi_0(\psi_0 - \psi_s) - \operatorname{ch}\psi_0 + \operatorname{ch}\psi_s]$ (8)

Using the obtained expression, it is possible to derive an expression for the total charge in this near-surface region of the semiconductor:

$$Q_s = 2qLn_i F(\psi_s; \psi_0) \quad (9)$$

Using expression (9) and the concept of the differential capacitance of the semiconductor:

$$C_s = \frac{q}{kT} \frac{dQ_s}{d\psi_s} \quad (10)$$

We obtain the expression for the capacitance of the bulk charge layer of the semiconductor:

$$C_s = S^2 q \epsilon \epsilon_0 n_i Q_s^{-1} [\exp\psi_s - \exp(-\psi_s) - 2\operatorname{sh}\psi_0] \quad (11)$$

Here: S is the area of the metal-dielectric-semiconductor structure [4].

To find the density of surface states N_{ss} localized at the semiconductor-insulator interface of a real metal-insulator-semiconductor structure, the expression connecting N_{ss} , the capacitance of the semiconductor space charge layer and the capacitance due to the presence of surface states are used as a function of the surface potential:

$$N_{ss} = \frac{1}{q^2} \left[\frac{C_s C_0}{C_0 - C_s} - C_s(\psi_s) \right] \quad (12)$$

A comparison of the calculated and experimental characteristics allows us to find the value of the surface charge density and its distribution over the width of the bandgap wave of the semiconductor. Figure 1 shows the theoretical (1) and experimental (2) low-frequency

capacitance-voltage characteristics of the metal-insulator-semiconductor (Al-SiO₂-n-Si) structure (normalized to the capacitance value of the dielectric layer), measured at room temperature, at a frequency of 5 KHz [5].

Pic. 1. theoretical (1) and experimental (2) low-frequency capacitance-voltage characteristics

Here, dependence 1 corresponds to the control structure, dependence 2 corresponds to the structure subjected to thermal effects at a temperature of 250°C for 30 minutes, and dependencies 3 and 4 correspond to structures subjected to thermal treatments at the same temperature for 60 and 120 minutes, respectively. One of the modifications of the low-frequency method, based on measuring the capacitance of a metal-dielectric-semiconductor structure, is the "quasistatic method".

The main advantage of this method is a more rigorous approximation to the conditions of thermodynamic equilibrium of charge carriers in a semiconductor during the measurement process. This approximation is achieved by the absence of a low-frequency test signal, the role of which is played by a bias voltage that varies linearly with time. Indeed, at low rates of change in bias voltage (dU/dt), all transient processes (at the interface, in the space charge region and in the inversion layer) manage to reach a state close to thermodynamic equilibrium. The displacement current (I) through the capacitance (C) of the metal-insulator-semiconductor structure can be expressed as follows:

$$I = \frac{dQ}{dt} = C \frac{dU}{dt} \quad (13)$$

Using a Ramping Bias Voltage $U = U_0 \pm \alpha t$ ($dU = \alpha dt$), when the condition $\alpha = \text{const}$ is met, it allows you to express the value of the structure's capacitance through the flowing current: $I = \alpha C$

Result. The value of the surface potential and the distribution of the density of surface states over the band gap of the semiconductor is determined from quasi-static C-U dependences [6]. To establish a correlation between the surface potential and the magnitude of the applied bias voltage, as in the conventional low-frequency method, the relation is used

$$\psi_s(U) = \int_{U_1}^{U_2} \left[1 - \frac{C(U)}{C_0} \right] dU + \Delta$$

Figure 2 shows the distribution of the density of surface states over the band gap of Si, obtained using the method described above. For measurements, we used metal-insulator-semiconductor structures made on the basis of hole-type silicon with a resistivity of 10 Ohm.cm, which underwent various heat treatment regimes.

Pic. 2. Distribution of the density of surface states over the width of the band gap of Si

The integration constant Δ in this relation is determined from comparison with the calculated C-U dependence.

Conclusion. The article presents modern models of solid surfaces and discusses modern methods for determining the electrical characteristics of surface layers and interphase boundaries. However, surface physics is a constantly evolving field of science. Methods for studying surfaces and interphase boundaries are also constantly being developed and improved.

REFERENCES

1. А.В. Гуртов. Твердотельная электроника. Петрозаводск. «ПетрГу» 2004. С.312.
2. Л.С. Берман, А.А. Лебедев . Емкостная спектроскопия глубоких центров в полупроводниках. Ленинград. «Наука». 1981. С.184.
3. Власов С.И., Базарбаев М.И., Назыров Д.Э., Эргашева М.А. Влияние давления на свойства структур металл-стекло-полупроводник //Доклады АН РУз. -Ташкент, 2006. - № 3.- С.24-27.
4. С.И.Власов. Электрические методы измерения параметров полупроводниковых структур. Ташкент. «Университет». 2007. С.172 .
5. С.З.Зайнабидинов, С.И. Власов, А.А. Насиров Не равновесные процессы на границе раздела полупроводник-диэлектрик. Ташкент. «Университет». 1995. С.112.
6. А.Я.Шик, Л.Г.Бакуева, С.Ф.Мусихин, С.А. Рыков. Физика низкоразмерных систем.С. Петербург. «Наука». 2001. С.160.